

**O'ZBEK TILIDAGI OMONIM SO'ZLAR VA ULARNING ZAMONAVIY TILSHUNOSLIKDAGI
O'RNI**

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ANNOTATSIYA: Omonim so'zlar nima? Ularning vazifalari, badiiy adabiyotda tajnis sa'natini va tuyuqni vujudga keltirishni o'rganish.

Kalit so'zlar: omonimlar, zamonaviy tilshunoslik, omonimiya, tuyuq.

Mustaqillik natijasida o'zbek tilshunosligi tom ma'noda mustaqil fan sifatida shakllandi va o'ziga xos ichki qurilishi o'zga tillar qoliplariga solmasdan o'rganish fanning ustuvor vazifasi qo'yildi. Buning natijasida o'zbek tilshunosligida tub burilish bo'lib bu jahon tilshunosligida e'tirof etildi. Ammo tan olib aytish kerakki, bugungi kunda turli o'quv lug'atlarini tayyorlash, omonimlar lug'atlari, antonimlar lug'atlari, sinonimlar lug'atlarining pedagogik asoslarini ishlab chiqish o'zbek tilshunosligining dolzarb muammolaridan biridir.

Omonim so'zlarnima? Ular qay tariqa shakllangan? Ushbu savollarga alohida to'xtalib o'tish lozim.

Omonimlar shakldosh so'zlar grekcha homos-“bir xil”, onoma-“nom “degan ma'nolarni ifodalab talaffuzi va yozilishi bir xil ammo atash ma'nosi har xil bo'lgan so'zlardir. Masalan, tut (daraxt), tut (harakat), yosh(ko'z yoshi), yosh (umr o'lchovi).

Omonim so'zlar bir xil so'z turkumi doirasida yoki har xil so'z turkumi doirasida bo'lishi mumkin. Masalan, bet (ot, yuzning salbiy bo'yoqdor shakli), bet (kitob beti), oshiq (oshiq-ot oshiq-fe'l oshiq-sifat).

Omonimiya hodisasi turli tillarda uchraydi, rus tilida uni V.Vinogradov, V.V.Shvedova, U.Yueng chuqur o'rgangan. O'zbek tilidagi singari rus tilida ham omonimlar juda ko'p, masalan o'roq qishloq xo'jaligi asbobi, o'roq bir tola qilib o'rilgan soch, o'roqqirg'oqdan oqib o'tadigan tor yer uchastkasi, kalit yerdan otilib chiqadigan prujina, kalit metall novda bo'lib uning yordamida qulf qulflanadi va ochiladi.

Omonimiya hodisasi xalq og'zaki ijodi namunasi bo'lgan askiya, hazil va latifalarda so'zo'yini hosil qilish uchun ishlatiladi. Omonimlar bizni nafaqat quvontiradi va zavqlantiradi nutqqa yorqin ifodali ranglar beradi. Omonim so'zlarni ishlatayoganimizda ehtiyotkorlik talab etiladi. Chunki gapirilayotgan nutqimizninoto'g'ri tushunilishi mumkin. Misol uchun "Bilimli yoshlar ko'chirilmoqda" jumlasining ma'nosi aniq, chunki bu yerdagi fe'l keyingi sinfga o'tish ma'nosini bildirishi mumkin va "yo'qolib, kamayib ketmoqda" ma'nosini idrok etish ham mumkin.

Omonim so'zlar og'zaki nutqimizda ham badiiy adabiyotda ham keng qo'llaniladi. Badiiy adabiyot tajnis (jinos) san'ati va she'riy janrlardan biri tuyuqni yuzaga keltiradi. 11 asrda yashab ijod qilgan Yusuf Xos Hojibning "Qutadg'u bilig" asarida Navoiy, Bobur tuyuqlarida omonim so'zlarning turli ko'rinishlarini uchratishimiz mumkin. Ularning ichidan Yusuf Xos Hojibning "Qutadg'u bilig" asaridan olingan parchani olsak:

Tili yolg'on erning jafaqilqiul, Jafa kimda ersao'sha yilqi ul

Kishi yolg'onindin tilama vafa

Bu bir so'zsinamisho'sha yilqi ul.

Birinchi baytda "yilqi ul" so'zi ot yoki otlar podasi ma'nosini anglatib keyingi baytdagi "yilqi ul" so'zi ancha yilga oid "aytilaverib siyqasi chiqqan" gap ma'nosini bildirayotgan so'z bilan omonimlik munosabatini hosil qilmoqda. Bu adibning so'zqo'llash mahoratining boyligini ko'rsatib beruvchi vosita sifatida xizmat qilmoqda.

Ba'zi omonimlar ona tilidagi so'zning yozilishi yoki aytilishiga boshqa tildan kirgan so'zning yozilishi yoki aytilishining mos kelib qolishi natijasida hosil bo'ladi. Masalan, tok- elektr quvvati, tok- uzum daraxti, to'rt- son, tort- ozuqa (ko'pincha o'zbek tilida to'rt deb talaffuz etiladi).

Ko'pincha omonimlar tildagi tovush o'zgarishlari natijasida hosil bo'ladi. Masalan, Ingliz tilida piece-bo'lak, peace-tinchlik, weak-kuchsiz, week-hafta, tear-ko'z yoshi, tear-yirtmoq kabi omonimlar tarkibidagi unli tovushlarning o'zgarishi natijasida hosil bo'lgan. Ingliz tilida so'zlarning yozilishi va talaffuzi o'rtasida katta farq mavjud. Unda har xil yoziluvchi so'zlar ham bir xil talaffuz qilinishi mumkin knight-farzin night-kechasi die-o'lmoq, dye-bo'yamoq kabi. Shu sababli bu tilda omonimlarning har xil turlari juda ko'p uchraydi. Ma'no jihatdan farqlanuvchi,

biroq aytilishi va yozilishi bir xil bo'lgan so'zlar to'liq omonimlar deb ataladi. Agar so'zlarning faqat yozilishi yoki talaffuzi bir xil bo'lsa, ular to'liq bo'lmagan omonimlar deyiladi.

Omonimlarning kelib chiqishida tildagi tovush o'zgarishlari, yozuv qoidalari va semantik siljishlar muhim manba bo'ladi. Omonimlarning ma'nolari nutq situatsiyasida kontekstda aniqlanadi.

O'zbekcha **leksemalarda** imkon boricha quyidagilar ta'kidlanadi:

- asli **fonemalar** (tovushlar) tarkibida farq bo'lganligi;
- yasama bo'lsa, qaysi **leksemadan** (sememadan) qaysi affiks bilan yasalganligi, omoleksemalarning yasalishi asosi va yasov ajralishi;

- asl ma'nosi va boshqalar.

O'zlashma **leksemalarda** imkon boricha quyidagilar ta'kidlanadi:

- asli qaysi til **leksemasi** ekanligi;
- o'sha tildagi tovush tizimi, grafik shakli;
- asl ma'nosi va boshqalar.

Ушбу мақолада ўқув луғатларининг умумий луғатлардан нафақат ҳажми, балки ундаги сўзларнинг танланиш мезонлари, луғат қисмларининг таркиби, жойлашуви – мегаструктураси билан ҳам фарқланиши, синоним ўқув луғатлар луғат мақоласи таркибида лексикографик пометалар (турли қисқартмалар, белгилар)га кам ўрин берилганлиги муҳокама қилинади.¹

This article is dedicated to the research of Adjusted meanings of Moral-spiritual concept defining units in the Uzbek language. And also analyzed the semantic analysis of grammatical shape lexemes of specialized meaning and provide a corresponding recommendation for lexicographical practice in the Uzbek language is one of the actual challenges of linguistics as today's challenge.²

¹ Гуландом Мирханова. (2022). СИНОНИМ СЎЗЛАР ЎҚУВ ЛУҒАТИНИНГ УМУМИЙ ТУЗИЛИШИ. *Yosh Tadqiqotchi Jurnal*, 1(2), 172–178. Retrieved from <http://2ndsun.uz/index.php/yt/article/view/90>

² Gulbahor, T. (2016). Adjusted Meanings of Moral-Spiritual Concept Defining Units. *ANGLISTICUM. Journal of the Association-Institute for English Language and American Studies*, 5(7), 40-45.

Корпус лингвистикасида семантик разметка, унинг теглар тизими, тег категориялари, семантик теглаш муаммолари, кўпмаънолилик ва омонимлик муаммосини ечиш масаласига оид қатор тадқиқотлар вужудга келган.³

The article discusses the research methods of Uzbek language syntax. In Uzbek linguistics, syntactic phenomena have been studied in detail since the 1930s, and several syntactic theories have emerged in this regard.⁴

The article examines the first dictionary in the Turkish language Mahmud Kashgaris "Devonu lugotit turk" in terms of a dictionary in accordance with the traditions of world lexicography and argues that it is the first appearance of modern complex dictionaries in the Turkish (Uzbek) language.⁵

Now studying scientific heritage, socio-political activities and acquaintance youth charity of our above-stated ancestors is considered one of the main urgent objectives of the modern intellectuals.⁶

This article covers the main place of small business and business in today's market economy. Including scientifically analyzed the development of small business and business, and the legal basis, at this time financially support small business and business, the latter is amended and the rules for this branch of national legislation are added.⁷

Мамлакатимиз тараққиётининг янги босқичида жамият ҳаётининг асосий негизи бўлмиш оилалар барқарор муҳитини мустаҳкамлаш ва бу масалаларда хотин-қизларнинг ўрни ва аҳамияти ошириш долзарб аҳамият касб этмоқда. Юртимиз аҳолисининг тенг ярмига яқинроғини ташкил этадиган хотин-қизлар жамиятнинг барча соҳаларида самарали фаолият юритмоқда.⁸

³ Ахмедова, Д. (2020). Семантик разметка тизимида тег гуруҳлари. *Oriental Art and Culture*, (III), 440-444.

⁴ Ergashevna, Y. N. (2021). ON METHODS OF RESEARCH OF UZBEK LANGUAGE SYNTAX. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 9(11), 22-28.

⁵ Bakhridinova, B. M. (2020). "DEVONU LUGOTIT TURK" AS A FIRST VIEW OF MODERN COMPLEX EDUCATIONAL DICTIONARIES. *Theoretical & Applied Science*, (4), 981-985.

⁶ Tolibjonovich, M. T. (2021). EASTERN RENAISSANCE AND ITS CULTURAL HERITAGE: THE VIEW OF FOREIGN RESEARCHERS. *ResearchJet Journal of Analysis and Inventions*, 2(05), 211-215.

⁷ Tolibjonovich, Madumarov T., and Gulomjonov O. R. Ogli. "Lombard Microcredit Organization Its Concept and Its Importance Today." *JournalNX*, vol. 6, no. 10, 2020, pp. 109-111.

⁸ Мадумарова Зиёдахон. (2022). ЯНГИЛАНАЁТГАН ЎЗБЕКИСТОНДА ГЕНДЕР МУАММОЛАРИНИ БАРТАРАФ ЭТИШДА АХЛОҚИЙ ҚАДРИЯТЛАРИНИНГ ЎРНИ. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6569712>

Badiiy adabiyotning qamrov darajasi keng sanaladi. Zero undagi janrlarning har biri insonning kamoloti uchun xizmat qiladi.⁹

Ushbu maqolada vatanparvarlik va millatparvarlik kabi axloqiy tushunchalar, hamda ularning mazmun mohiyati Somerset Moem qalamiga mansub bo'lgan "Bo'ysunmagan" ("The Unconquered") deb nomlangan hikoyaning syujeti va bosh qahramonlarning xarakterini tahlil qilish orqali ochib beriladi¹⁰

The article examines the role of dictionaries and their content, and, in particular, defines the role of explanatory dictionaries, from their compilation to their semantic meaning. Examples of lexical units and their meanings are given. Attention is drawn to the structure of explanatory dictionaries as a constituent part of the dictionaries as a whole.¹¹

In this article are given the importance, role, types of the family in modern society. Its development from ancient times till present is widely described in this article.¹²

The widespread introduction of new pedagogical technologies in teaching students of higher educational institutions and the effective use of innovative technologies are the main support for improving the quality of education.¹³

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar:

1. Гуландом Мирханова. (2022). СИНОНИМ СЎЗЛАР ЎҚУВ ЛУФАТИНИНГ УМУМИЙ ТУЗИЛИШИ. *Yosh Tadqiqotchi Jurnal*, 1(2), 172–178. Retrieved from <http://2ndsun.uz/index.php/yt/article/view/90>

⁹ Oripova Kamola. (2022). O'ZBEK VA FRANSUZ TILLARIDAGI MAQOLLARDA JON KONSEPTINING IFODALANISHI. *Yosh Tadqiqotchi Jurnal*, 1(3), 398–408. Retrieved from <http://2ndsun.uz/index.php/yt/article/view/209>

¹⁰ Pulatova Sabina. (2022). VATANPARVARLIK AXLOQNING ASOSIY TUSHUNCHALARIDAN BIRI SIFATIDA. *Yosh Tadqiqotchi Jurnal*, 1(3), 357–368. Retrieved from <http://2ndsun.uz/index.php/yt/article/view/205>

¹¹ Bobomurodova, L. K. (2021). FEATURES OF THE COMPILATION OF MODERN EXPLANATORY DICTIONARIES.

¹² Nasriddinovich, A. A. (2020). THE FEATURES OF APPEARING FAMILY IN MODERN SOCIETY. *European science review*, (3-4), 69-72.

¹³ Jamoliddinovich, U. B. (2022). FUNDAMENTALS OF EDUCATION QUALITY IN HIGHER EDUCATION. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH* ISSN: 2277-3630 *Impact factor: 7.429, 11(01), 149-151.*

2. Gulbahor, T. (2016). Adjusted Meanings of Moral-Spiritual Concept Defining Units. ANGLISTICUM. Journal of the Association-Institute for English Language and American Studies, 5(7), 40-45.
3. Ахмедова, Д. (2020). Семантик разметка тизимида тег гуруҳлари. Oriental Art and Culture, (III), 440-444.
4. Ergashevna, Y. N. (2021). ON METHODS OF RESEARCH OF UZBEK LANGUAGE SYNTAX. Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal, 9(11), 22-28.
5. Bakhridinova, B. M. (2020). "DEVONU LUGOTIT TURK" AS A FIRST VIEW OF MODERN COMPLEX EDUCATIONAL DICTIONARIES. Theoretical & Applied Science, (4), 981-985.
6. Tolibjonovich, M. T. (2021). EASTERN RENAISSANCE AND ITS CULTURAL HERITAGE: THE VIEW OF FOREIGN RESEARCHERS. ResearchJet Journal of Analysis and Inventions, 2(05), 211-215.
7. Tolibjonovich, Madumarov T., and Gulomjonov O. R. Ogli. "Lombard Microcredit Organization Its Concept and Its Importance Today." *JournalNX*, vol. 6, no. 10, 2020, pp. 109-111.
8. Мадумарова Зиёдахон. (2022). ЯНГИЛАНАЁТГАН ЎЗБЕКИСТОНДА ГЕНДЕР МУАММОЛАРИНИ БАРТАРАФ ЭТИШДА АХЛОҚИЙ ҚАДРИЯТЛАРНИНГ ЎРНИ. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6569712>
9. Oripova Kamola. (2022). O'ZBEK VA FRANSUZ TILLARIDAGI MAQOLLARDA JON KONSEPTINING IFODALANISHI. *Yosh Tadqiqotchi Jurnal*, 1(3), 398-408. Retrieved from <http://2ndsun.uz/index.php/yt/article/view/209>
10. Pulatova Sabina. (2022). VATANPARVARLIK AXLOQNING ASOSIY TUSHUNCHALARIDAN BIRI SIFATIDA. *Yosh Tadqiqotchi Jurnal*, 1(3), 357-368. Retrieved from <http://2ndsun.uz/index.php/yt/article/view/205>
11. Bobomurodova, L. K. (2021). FEATURES OF THE COMPILATION OF MODERN EXPLANATORY DICTIONARIES.
12. Nasriddinovich, A. A. (2020). THE FEATURES OF APPEARING FAMILY IN MODERN SOCIETY. *European science review*, (3-4), 69-72.
13. Jamoliddinovich, U. B. (2022). FUNDAMENTALS OF EDUCATION QUALITY IN HIGHER EDUCATION. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH* ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429, 11(01), 149-151.